

Parameterization of New Religion utilizing EPEMC and Western Humanistic Egalitarianism as a guide.

Engineering A Reasonable, Scientific Open-Source (cultless) Religion for the
Aquarian Age and Scientific Period

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM
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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the possibility of replacing (over a very long period) old bureaucratic, institutionalized religions, which divide people despite their common origins in the Archaic and Transition Periods¹, with a religion based upon the miracles and mysteries of Science, along with humanistic egalitarianism. Parameters are discussed around a select few ideal tenets. The topic of God is left to the background of history, or will be discussed in future papers. The primary focus of the paper is to apply a litmus test of beliefs, in order to aid mankind in fulfilling a basic human need. The absence of a modernized religion has enabled cults to take advantage of people seeking spiritual help, but disillusioned by systemic beliefs. New Age ideas make proto-scientific claims, and are for the most part harmless, however people are reluctant to join “fringe” ideas. An open-source, but disciplined in time-tested religious values and traditional norms, religion would be able to provide both answers (historical or otherwise) and mysteries to help people continue their journey. The open-source “code” also will enable multi-cultural adoption and standardizations which are reasonable but do not violate Human Rights.

Additionally the paper explores what Power could be made central to this: the *connecting interweb of electricity and magnetism (and radiation)* which pervades the cosmos. Instead of worshipping scientists as the new bishops and popes, people could directly access the source of power through internal and external exploration

Keywords: religion - electricity - spirit - miracle - Birkeland Polyphase Superweb

¹ Periods are discussed in [1], Table 1

Purpose and Synopsis

Five things are obvious about humanity now, considering the unreasonable and trifling² “limitations”³ in resources, IQ scarcity⁴, and penchant for war⁵:

1. Mankind has not been able to healthily cope with the disasters and catastrophes, and has resorted to massive expenditures in entertainment, end of the world media, and warheads (literal weapons of the gods)⁶. Some of this is exacerbated by the industrial warfare economy, but the willpower to justify it is only maintained through a generalized fear and anxiety of nebulous forces⁷.
2. Mankind will struggle in the transition through the Scientific Period from Religious Period⁸ so long as there is clinging to archaic forms of state and social control level Religion. Extremism is but one example. The result has been to religify Science (forming Scientism⁹), which is both wasteful and distracting, as well as aggravates social violence and enables gaps in Science to form which re-fill with antiquated beliefs that are quasi-religious (such as Flat Earth). This is the fault of Science, yes, but Science is composed of scientists, who are human and religious. It is natural that as more common folks and less of the noble classes practice STEM, they will drag inherent superstitious belief systems into the STEM fields.
3. Conversely, Science is a poor religion. Scientism has almost nothing in the form of spiritual practical guidance for humans. Psychology, as a study, and neuroscience have denied the human soul, and participated in grotesque, cold acts of barbarism (such as electroshock therapy and lobotomies) meant to make a study of the human physique and psyche while masquerading as a form of therapy.¹⁰
4. Humans will form new religions as they abandon old ones. These, without guidance, will not be well engineered but will include almost certainly several hundred years worth of impractical mishmash of New Age and Old Age beliefs, half-understood and unverified scientific and pseudoscientific claims, various levels of wisdom and barbarism, and in sum total, a general abandonment of some of the original virtuous purposes of Religion, such as: charity, social shelter, morality, strengthening of the nuclear family, etc... This “throwing the baby out with the bathwater” appears to be a wholesale behavior rather than selective, perhaps in response to negative religious stimuli¹¹, perhaps in anticipation or pressure gradients applied by media¹², state sponsorship¹³, corporate marketing

² Money for space programs but not housing homeless and feeding children, etc...

³ Although energy is abundant it is relatively difficult to obtain. However, humanity has made homes into energy deserts which support only human life and little else... so it seems a bit ridiculous in a sea of charge above and below to claim that energy is “hard” to get. What seems difficult, rather, is willpower!

⁴ The average IQ of the most populated regions of the world is, unfortunately still rather low. Even the US and UK averages are under 100 at 98 and 99 apiece. Some countries in Africa are as low as 59 or 60. Most of their brightest minds will leave there and come to the West, and many will not go back home. Hence: relative scarcity. An excessive amount of IQ is concentrated in places like Silicon Valley, Singapore, Tokyo, Brussels, etc...

⁵ Not the standard anthropomorphic biological competition, such as exhibited in tribes, or in revenge killings, but industrialized, manufactured war and propaganda apparatus.

⁶ [5]

⁷ Aliens, Climate Change, Patriarchy, Nuclear Energy etc...

⁸ mid-1800's

⁹ <https://www.aaas.org/programs/dialogue-science-ethics-and-religion/what-scientism>

¹⁰ Health is best defined by Hippocrates, “First, do **no** harm.”

¹¹ ISIS, cults, Catholic pedophile coverup, corrupt preachers, etc...

¹² Such as Social Justice (ie, postmodernist) assaults on science: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3463968/>

¹³ Such as China's tendency to apply widespread social policy; North Korea, Iran, Germany, Iceland, etc...

strategies¹⁴ ¹⁵, and banker-controlled-market forces¹⁶ which destabilize or “jerk around”¹⁷ labor forces¹⁸ and populations.¹⁹

5. If, however, the Force²⁰ - as it were - were understood as a centralizing “cosmic pole”,²¹ then through a series of generally widely accepted as true social axioms, principles, norms, and values (etc...) that represent the cutting edge in human history²² could form a ‘revolving axis’²³ which would renew the ancient behaviors that rally humanity together through survivalist periods. But in this case: to survive against mankind himself.

In light of this the only things left to determine are: I) which norms, etc... represent the best of humanism and egalitarian values that II) meet the standards of universal (ie natural) appeal, practicality, utility, and spiritual as well as psychological wholesomeness, and III) also align with lessons learned from EPEMC, utilizing the top research in science, alternative science, medicine, alternative medicine, history, alternative history, mainstream and alternative religion, that also respect the mythic past in anthropomorphic, planetary, and archetypal forms while not strangling future growth²⁴, restricting human freedom²⁵, setting unrealistically high bars²⁶ for common folk²⁷ and leaders²⁸, and finally: respecting the concrete political²⁹, social³⁰, economic³¹, and environmental realities³² that Earth and humans face today.

This paper cannot address **every** parameter, nor should it. As part of the parameters it must remain as loose enough a framework to both provide a termite mound like structure but give the room and freedom of chaos and enable each individual, group, locality, and state to determine its own normative acceptances, policies, and cultural decisions.³³

¹⁴ Pepsi, Cigarette companies, Levi-strauss, Nike, etc... all engage in marketing methods that manipulate traditional roles in society and family.

¹⁵ Gillette: <https://www.bbc.com/news/newsbeat-46874617> ; marketing messing with family values goes back to the 1950s

¹⁶ Literally, the Federal Reserve constantly moves the economic bars

¹⁷ See: Special Economic Zones, IMF, WTO, CFR, and World Bank

¹⁸ See: International Trade Deals (NAFTA, etc...)

¹⁹ See: Chinese migrant crisis, and US-Mexico border war, and EU/Africa Refugee/Migrant Slave-trade

²⁰ Plasma-electromagnetism: the Unified Aether Field

²¹ See: [7] and “Saturn Myth,” by D. Talbott

²² Last 200-300 years.

²³ An orbit of behavior, if you will. A social Maypole.

²⁴ Of economy, intelligence, technology, healthcare, and of course the new god: entertainment.

²⁵ Including Speech, Protest, Report, Anticipatory Self-Defense, Search & Seizure, Privacy, Profile, Property, Identity, Education, Diet, Belief, and Economic Opportunity. Hereon referred to as “Human Rights”

²⁶ Such as “Become a buddha,” or “an immortal,” or “be like a child to enter the kingdom,” etc... Or “never sin.”

²⁷ From the homeless and mad to corporate managers, comptrollers, bean-counters, and mechanics; blue & white collar.

²⁸ Politicians, religious leaders, teachers, celebrities, etc...

²⁹ Right vs Left; Globalist vs. Populist; Capitalist vs. Socialist; East vs. West, etc... “Spheres of Influence and Affluence”

³⁰ Religious differences, racial cultural norm differences, preferences, tribalist vs individualist, civilized vs aboriginal, etc...

³¹ Disenfranchised vs. poor vs. 1st world poor vs. uneducated poor vs middle class vs upper class vs uber-rich vs elite

³² Climate Changes due to solar and magnetospheric changes, deforestation, plastic ocean, oil dependence, etc...

³³ An example might be if Japan decided to make Sumo Wrestling only male, but in international competition the Olympics one day added Sumo and required Japan to post a female team as well. A humanistic ethics for the future must allow both directions, without denying the right of either. Both are understandable within their religious ethos, and this parameterization, requiring a *natural* outcome that doesn't lead to war or strife, must allow both, and peace between disagreeing parties, if no agreement can be met. But it cannot be a globalist-only ethos, because that will strengthen populist gradients and destabilize local geo-politics. It's the butterfly effect in application. The Religious ethos in this paper must engineer solutions which respect this complex web, because the Internet requires it.

An Example Set of Principles

As an exercise in applying these criterium, here are a few humanistic, spiritual practices and/or beliefs for us to see if they can be included or discluded via the application of parameters as well as EPEMC 'rigorous' dialectics or debate.³⁴

So, for example, some things which are recommended for spiritual and physical health:

- Meditate daily
 - Prayer, mindfulness, or mental relaxation
 - Mantras or repetitious affirmations, repetitions of prayer script, occasionally with use of hands (rubbing or holding objects)
- Focus on lightening (and lighting) the heart region
 - Turning light inwards
 - Inner smile, etc...
- Breathe in mentally guided, time-regulated, relaxed manners, several times daily
- Keep lots of friends
- Laugh daily, smile often, and do not hold grudges.
- Work honestly and hardily, but observe a day of rest.

It isn't necessary to make a complete list, or even a thorough list, in order to prove the principles.

Meditation, especially daily meditation - in the form of prayers, mindfulness based relaxation, or emptying the mind, etc... - is ubiquitous in all forms of religion, and has been shown to have numerous health benefits for the mind and body, and has even been verified in fMRI as to its usefulness and difference with common thought patterns³⁵. What's interesting is where the concepts of bio-energy, Qi³⁶, prajna, ru'ach³⁷, etc... meets with PEMC, becoming EPEMC³⁸, in both ancient Oriental sciences³⁹ as well as shown in modern clinical application.⁴⁰

Mantras, or repetitious affirmations or utilizing the hands has been shown to further activate regions of the brain which would facilitate similar locations associated with relaxation. Also, as the cerebellum is below the occipital region of the cortex where visualization is controlled, it would stand to reason that mutual stimulation might enhance the function and circulation in both.

As for EPEMC, it views each of these as a means of reducing signal overload of the circuits, and biomedically lengthening the lifespan of cells via metabolic reduction. Studies definitely correlate caloric⁴¹ and reproductive⁴² metabolism⁴³ with oxidation⁴⁴ (free radical) and telomerase degradation⁴⁵.

³⁴ As rigorous as a non-theological paper can get. Looking into theologic didactics throughout European history, the reader must agree with the author that this paper neither can nor should compete with nor would it want to, given the nature of modern time constraints in a click-bait and/or sound-byte culture.

³⁵ [15]

³⁶ <http://bluelotushealth.com/whatisqi/>

³⁷ <http://bluelotushealth.com/what-is-qi-for-judeo-christians/>

³⁸ [10]

³⁹ ibid.

⁴⁰ [9]

⁴¹ <https://www.newscientist.com/article/2164602-calorie-restriction-may-extend-lifespan-by-changing-your-sleep/>

⁴² <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3694819/>

⁴³ <https://www.nature.com/scitable/topicpage/dna-replication-and-causes-of-mutation-409>

⁴⁴ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12031895>

⁴⁵ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2842081/>

Focusing on the heart has the benefit of conforming to all ancient traditions' religious and spiritual aims, many ancient societies' "psychology"⁴⁶, matching health claims such as "lightening the heart" while simultaneously matching PEMC concepts of reducing *load* upon the body's electric circuit, by reducing either mechanical taxation or psycho-somatic electrical drain (ie, depression). If there *is* a golden light, perhaps on some other dimension, or perhaps coming from a fiber optic like projection in the nervous system, then - as light is an electric circuit or a propagating of the electromagnetic forces and quantized charge (photonic energy) - it makes sense for the heart to be naturally enhanced in strength and positive function, as it would surge the circuits with positive energy.

By contrast, techniques such as the Inner Smile appear to rely purely upon a psycho-somatic method, which unless there is a specific religious objection, can be considered "besides the point" from an EPEMC perspective. At any rate, there wouldn't be any problem in including the practice in a scientifically valid New Religion; unless again there is a specific religious prohibition, of which the author has never heard.

Next, in considering breathing techniques, of which there are many and their focuses are also manifold: we will just generally assign breathing to the increase, or enhancement of an oxygenation signal (meaning high metabolism and cellular performance). Consider the religious dynamic: no religion could possibly protest against deep breathing, which calms the heart and mind. Meanwhile, excellent science shows that deep breathing enhances health.⁴⁷ And finally, oxygenation would undoubtedly correspond to electrical theories,⁴⁸ particularly with respect to inhaling negative ions, which are manufactured by waves and waterfalls⁴⁹ and forests. These environments induce serious healthy benefits⁵⁰, and all of them have been shown to be electrically active; a fact which is utilized by fish^{51 52} and birds,⁵³ for example.

When it comes to certain lifestyle suggestions, such as "keeping many friends" etc... if they are not electrically or physics related, EPEMC does not have much to say about them. So the question is could such a thing *ever* violate the standards we have set above? In a balanced and/or reasonable-minded person, the answer will be "no" 100% of the time. Lifestyle suggestions which are supported by research from the NatGeo "Blue Zone Project"⁵⁴ will be particularly difficult to argue with because they already support the spiritualism inherent in all of the world's peaceful, legitimate religions, and many of its cults. Therefore it would be difficult in an objective setting for anyone, much less a megalomaniacal cult-leader or terrorist, to debate them point for point and undermine them. Therefore in the creation of a New Religion, it is advisable that such lifestyle suggestions be included. These may include, for example,

- ❖ Eat wholesome foods.
- ❖ Drink and consecrate water, for it is holy.
- ❖ Think wholesome thoughts.
- ❖ Be charitable and kind.
- ❖ Do good for the greatest number of people.
- ❖ Do not forget the weak or small.
- ❖ Expand your mind.
- ❖ Grow daily into your fullest being.

⁴⁶ Such as the Chinese word for heart and mind being the same, "xin" 心

⁴⁷ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5709795/>

⁴⁸ <http://bluelotushealth.com/signal-pulse/>

⁴⁹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6213340/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3546779/>

⁵¹ <https://news.njit.edu/electric-fish-augmented-reality-reveal-how-animals-actively-sense-world-around-them>

⁵² <https://www.uni-bonn.de/news/304-2018>

⁵³ <http://spie.org/newsroom/1804-understanding-how-birds-navigate?ArticleID=x37204&SSO=1>

⁵⁴ https://www.ted.com/talks/dan_buettner_how_to_live_to_be_100?language=en

- ❖ Be broad-minded.
- ❖ Conserve resources.
- ❖ Respect others' time and be punctual.
- ❖ Be organized and appreciative.
- ❖ Have a good, positive moral attitude.
- ❖ Accept others' failures with the least amount of judgment possible, etc...

Such a moralistic set of values has been put forward in rare documents before, notably the Daodejing, Sermon on the Mount, and Desiderata⁵⁵, which is a very recent document.

Laughing daily and working hardily are the last for us to consider. In the case of the former, it has the effect of lightening one's heart load, and others' as well, for it is well known that mirth is contagious. Comedy, in general - even mean-spirited comedy - has the power to lift up multitudes of people by reducing their heart load. Since our humanistic New Religion requires tolerance, it will be not up to a groupthink to create a heavy pressure upon the comedian to not harm people, but up to market forces which will dictate if the message is unacceptable. This will eliminate gestapo censors which try to curtail art and humor (that they oppose), by being socially and spiritually intolerant.

As for working hardily, it would be difficult to find any religion which wants you to be lazy, but in a single case the author knows of: Taoism. This is ironic because Daoists are known for their endurance. But there is a tradition of levity in life which cannot be said to be outwardly strongly compatible with the beliefs of, say, the Amish. However, upon closer examination, it can be said that Daoists have, historically, not been as lazy as much as drunk, and drink is common to all religions. Moreover cloud-walkers by habit are not lazy but farmers, who pick food for locals. Some are mere beggars and users of the poor, but can such faux-Zen masters ever be said to be religious if they are self-centered? So it is difficult to justify the hatred of hard work.

Medically TCM and other similar holistic paths warn against overwork, but that can be said to be medical and a compassion. The common populace is working too hard, especially in Asian countries like South Korea and Singapore. And the lack of rest can be said to be a spiritual and mental drain that has led to terrible situations, like gang-rapes, suicide epidemics, and mass depression and video game addiction. So it is good that ideals such as those in the Desiderata and Taoism temper hard work. But hard work is also good for creating wealth for many, and for sweating out toxins and poisons. It also is said that the "idle mind is the Devil's playground." Then let the opposite prevent devilry: professionalism and purpose.

Can these types of values square themselves with EPEMC? Certainly again either through lightening the heart and channels, to electrify it, or by promoting ion flush of the lymphatic system, fascia, and sweat pores in the skin, which is known since the Shang Han Lun to prevent diseases. In fact, in the author's opinion, it is vital for health to sweat and sweat regularly. Why should this violate EPEMC?

So are these humanistic and egalitarian? Unfortunately not all people are born humorous, charming, quick to a smile, or capable of spreading joy. For some their mere polarity drives away people via frequency disagreement, and such people often become "loners" and may take to depressing thoughts, fears, or negativities and anxieties. This is a difficult situation to remedy, for these people wish to be loved (usually) and to spread love, humor, gaiety and compassion, but it is difficult for them. And consider the introverts: in some cases it is mentally unhealthy for them to be around many people, and only a few friends are necessary to keep them healthy. They may find that they are made worse by forcing them into such situations: which is not humanistic. It cannot be expected for everyone to be a morning person, a cheerleader, a bringer-up (and amplifier), or a transformer or generator. Some people must be allowed to be resistors, potentiometers, etc... in social circuits. That is: draining and potentially, lazy as well.⁵⁶

⁵⁵ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Desiderata> (1927)

⁵⁶ For a humorous religious take, read from Arabian Nights, "Muhammed Hight-Lazy Bones" https://www.wollamshram.ca/1001/Vol_4/tale37.htm

So the last values we introduced must be modified:

- ❑ Laugh easily, smile naturally, do not act upon grudges
- ❑ Work contentedly and thoroughly, to the best of your ability

But hold it, this last idea, which is distinctly western, and may actually prevent worldwide acceptance. While the West holds that people everywhere else are lazy, or lack work ethic, this is not so. It is only that western values of working excessively are post-industrial hangovers, while agrarian societies generally know how to take breaks and appreciate calm periods, to rest body and mind and re-charge spirits. So we must amend again: Work contentedly and thoroughly, to the level necessary for fulfilling the work appropriately given all circumstances related to the tasks at hand.

Comparisons with current religious Values

The difficulty in engineering a new religion is in the obtaining of agreement from practitioners of old religions. Alternatively, in those who have made their faith a form of non-faith (such as atheism), which may hold some bitterness to religion, though ironically having faith in their non-faith, it may be difficult to get adoption and signatories, willingly. In both cases, because of the humanistic egalitarian principle and Human Rights, these people **must be allowed to remain as they are, teach as they will, protest even**; but they must be prevented from utilizing force, policy, extremism, violence, and criminality to battle society or the New Religion.

This is more or less the policy used to deal with aborigines of certain islands or forests. Governments create a protective sphere to leave them be, and do not prosecute them if civilized people violate the sphere and are killed. This tolerance of their non-adherence is strange considering the intolerance of the homeless and vagrant within cities, but nevertheless it is a difference observed due to geographical difference.

The overriding principles here are both successful forms of Buddhistic proselytism:

1. Be a friend in the orchid room: your actions and bearing will cause people to question their lower frequency beliefs and adopt more healthy, balanced ideals. This is the 'scent' upon them when they leave which reminds them of you.
2. Present, but do not expect.⁵⁷

Now, will it also happen that people from various parts of the world, in adapting a scientific, cult-less, servant-leader based New Religion, find reason to disagree, which is cultural, linguistic, or racially based? Yes,

⁵⁷ *"If the bodhisattvas mahasattva in the evil age hereafter wish to preach this sutra, they should abide by four rules. First, they should abide by the practices and associations proper for bodhisattvas so that they can expound this sutra for the sake of living beings. Manjushri, what do I mean by the practices of a bodhisattva/mahasattva? If a bodhisattva mahasattva takes his stand on perseverance, is gentle and compliant, never violent, and never alarmed in mind; and if with regard to phenomena he takes no action but observes the true aspect of phenomena without acting or making any distinction, then this I call the practices of a bodhisattva mahasattva.*

...

"He should not delight in nurturing underage disciples, shramaneras, or children, and should not delight in sharing the same teacher with them. He should constantly take pleasure in sitting in meditation, and being in quiet surroundings learn to still his mind. Manjushri, these are what I call the things he should first of all associate himself with.

"Next, the bodhisattva mahasattva should view all phenomena as empty, that being their true aspect. They do not turn upside down, do not move, do not regress, do not revolve. They are like empty space, without innate nature, beyond the reach of all words. They are not born, do not emerge, do not arise. They are without name, without form, without true being. They are without volume, without limits, without hindrance, without barriers. It is only through causes and conditions that they exist, but because of upside-downness, errors are born. Therefore I say that he should constantly delight in viewing the aspect of phenomena as this. This is what I call the second thing that the bodhisattva mahasattva should associate himself with." ~ Ch. 14, Lotus Sutra <https://www.nichirenlibrary.org/en/Isoc/Content/14>

this is natural. Studies show that people typically prefer mates and ideas from people of a similar race to their own, much less language and customs. So it is to be expected that a worldwide New Religion would result in a similar evolutionary diversification as has happened since the one world religion of the world of the Man-King/Fertility God of the Midnight Sun fell, and when the Tower of Babel (Cosmic Mountain) was cast down.⁵⁸

In such cases although war could not be tolerated, customs could be respected, if they do not violate Human Rights. It would be necessary for government to **not** be used in crusades or economic reprisals which create blood oaths and long lasting hatreds. But if a people or persons would not recant in their desire to have vengeance for religious differences, then they would need be isolated. If they would make war, then they would need to be wiped out, for the greater protection of the rest of the species and promotion of peace. For peace breeds both profit and enterprise, and encourages the intermingling of population energies, DNA, ideas, customs, etc... which would eventually lead to a homeostasis of difference. A cellular exchange akin to organ equilibrium in the body: separate but useful and necessary, within their own geographic cavities. To some degree mankind has always lived this way... however, it has never really been efficiently done until the League of Nations first introduced the concept. However the League of Nations and then the United Nations failed to include more than a legal worldwide standard, but a moral and religious ethos worldwide standard. Nor could it, because after all no one would have stayed. This was before the internet, and before mass commercialization and abandonment of the religious spirit for a hedonistic or nihilistic spirit of competitive consumerism, which has generated so much despondence and homelessness that it has enabled mass infection of terroristic paradigms⁵⁹.

It could be left to time for these all to sort out in a sort of *immune* like response. But as has been seen with the failed Socialism experiment⁶⁰, even if one *organ* has seen and experienced it, if separate generations elsewhere have not, the lessons of history may not provide adequate immunity to the failed virulent idea.⁶¹ If a subsequent weakening of religious moralities has also given way to rampant greed and repugnant materialism⁶² which denies the human soul and disrespects nature and the unity of male and female, the immune system will fail to be strong enough to prevent the spread anyhow. This is dangerous not only because it is potentially deadly⁶³, but because it wastes time, and irreplaceable resources⁶⁴. It also wastes spaces.⁶⁵

Can a New Religion directly deal with these? No, because it is humanistic and passive. However, by teaching the youth, they become the leadership. Also, the government in the west and increasingly abroad is becoming more tolerant of religions that are not native (except Islam, which remains strongly immune due to internal regulatory methods⁶⁶) since, after all the gods are gone and the moon and sun are no longer worshiped. People naturally ask “why” they should be angry and hostile to different ideas, especially when they are despondent with failed paradigms which do not give them a holistic spiritual toolbox to deal with the

⁵⁸ Both symbolically, and the physical tower location, which would have been a symbolic effort that concretely represented both the fall of the God and the fall of Man, and the “sin” which led to the death of the Fertile Crescent and the cataclysms.

⁵⁹ ISIS, school shooters, jihadism, etc...

⁶⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_former_communist_states_and_socialist_states

⁶¹

<https://www.victimsofcommunism.org/witnessblog/2018/4/19/forty-four-percent-of-millennials-prefer-socialism-do-they-know-what-it-means>

⁶² Hoarding, “making it rain”, tax breaks for ‘the 0.1%’, making it illegal to feed homeless, etc...

⁶³ Genocide, mostly; but also starvation.

⁶⁴ Oil, species, certain woods (like cork), etc...

⁶⁵ Soil, sky, potable water, oceans, city lots, etc...

⁶⁶ In Indonesia and many countries they have police patrols to keep tabs on Muslims. These function as a form of thought control. Muslims in the West don’t usually have much to do with non-Muslims outside of work and school settings, and many have their own schools. It is common, therefore that westerners do not know the first thing about Islamic beliefs or cultural practices. So much so that whole communities with un-Western beliefs and practices have entered the West and gone largely unnoticed.

realities of life. Often they do not know of successful spirit sciences which do not fail, though they are not 'in vogue' or even in power of influence.⁶⁷

The Real Difficulty...

Actually, the real difficulty lies not in creating or educating in a New Religion. After all, there are generations of spiritual transients who cannot "find a home" and are looking. Humans cannot help but look as we are genetically and culturally hardwired to be faithful. Even atheists are faithful to Science, and hence create Scientism unwillingly.

The difficulty is in getting people to rationally submit faith to a passive type religion, when they are used to passionate - even violent - belief as the **modus normalis et operandus**. Consider, briefly, the difficulties of Unitarianism. They are too Christian for agnostics, let alone atheists and too New Age for Christians. They are too passive for Buddhists, and too blase for Daoists. They are altogether too limp-wristed for the general desires of humanity. Without hot-heart-passion for spirituality people turn down and tune out. They become more passionate on Sunday for football than they do with church. Can Unitarianism, therefore, ever hope to capture a wide appeal? A Unitarian would tell you something like, "Well, we don't want to. We want to be there for the people who want a passive, quiet religion, and are okay with the loud and obnoxious being in their loud, obnoxious religions." They'd probably feel guilty for being judgmental, after saying it!

This is where the science comes in, and at the appropriate place. While Science and the scientific method can do nothing **directly** for spiritual matters, and in some cases may harm people spiritually through cold, barbaric experimentation or animal cruelty, it isn't short on the energy that provides *real juice* and passionate life-blood to masses yearning for the supernatural: miracles and exploration of mystery.

It is imperative, then, that Science stop advertising itself as *normal* and devoid of miracles. Biomedicine is replete with miracles! And as for the exploration of mystery, it seems that astronomy and archaeology are rife with problems and ready for not only *more exploration*, including of the cosmos, but for *re-exploration* of previously "settled" matters⁶⁸, which after all are not settled and were probably misinterpreted.⁶⁹

Science cannot directly be religion; but it can be its lifeblood. And it should be, or else violence and ridiculous superstitions will remain that lifeblood. This is not only foolish and dangerous, it is a huge waste of government spending, since after all a healthy spiritual society - any society - is a secure one. It is therefore a matter of national and international security that the Scientific Period be defined not by *denying God* and certainly not trying to kill Him: but by providing the continual evidence of *humanity's specialness, uniqueness, and wonderful place in the cosmos*. Let Nationalism be replaced with Humanism. Let Pride and Racism be replaced with Traditional Values and appreciation of culture. But, after all, these passive (water-like) values and behaviors may prove slow to take and replace the aggressive (fire-like) values of current religions (including atheism, Scientism, and veganism).

⁶⁷ Taoism, Buddhism, Zoroastrianism, Shintoism... even balanced Christianity has given way to militant evangelism. But this form of evangelism is antithetical to Christian momentum and remains difficult to sustain without Fear of the Other. Unfortunately the globalists and jihadists, in their quest for power have gifted an ancient enemy in Islam as this impetus of recruitment for a less tolerant Christianity. However there are distinct differences between balanced Islamic practice and jihadism, just as there are between average Christians and ultra-right wing evangelists. It is both an energy difference and a pressure gradient difference. Letting them both drain into the extreme form to swell the potential gradient will only add fuel to the masses for a large, ie violent, transfer later. This is why Europe's situation is particularly distressing.

⁶⁸ Such as Dark Matter and the Big Bang

⁶⁹ Uniformitarianism and denial of diffusion and the electric nature of the Universe.

What is Needed

Miracles, it has been shown, are not enough. They are easy to believe in person, but difficult both with distance and with time, and impossible to keep them straight with all details intact. No amount of stories about people returning from comas or seeing the Afterlife have led to a permanent revival of Judeo-Christian traditions. Movies get released and these (contrariwise to attempts and intentions) cheapen the experience of the miracle.

So how was it done *before*... mostly before the Religious Period when spiritual fire was replaced with the zeal of population control and with bureaucracy?

The power of the gods was manifest: namely “fire and brimstone”; literally super-lightning bolts and even intercelestial arc-discharge, and of course “hail” (cometary rock). When Dao was manifest in the sky, the power of the God (and his four ‘winds’ which were plasma streamers) was felt, seen, heard, and made manifest through electrokinetic or electrogravitic miracles.

Mankind himself tried to rival these with monumental architecture and lifting larger and larger stones with unknown powers that we have *forgotten* in our foolishness. Stones so large we cannot even move them with our best cranes!⁷⁰

How, therefore, can we achieve this not by accident, or by being the unhappy recipient of death, destruction, famine, flood, conflagration, continent-shifting, radiation/flares, or cometary impact?

Use the Force...

There were three compelling aspects to “Star Wars” (A New Hope) which made it internationally appealing and potent, causing people to spend more money upon Star Wars than the GDP of some countries.

1. The Hero’s Journey or Warrior Path, a Campbellian formula which is present throughout the world, describing the “tribulations of Heracles (Mars)”
2. The destruction of the Death Star/Evening Star (Venus) whose plasma death ray extended from its center and wipes out the planet. (Our obsessive fear)
3. The use of a quasi-mystic, but **palpable**, potent, real *force* that enables the hero to manifest the power yielded from father-to-son (Father to Sun, as it were) in order to defeat the darkness.

Is it any surprise that the globalist cabal, which is reportedly rife with evil and barbaric practices like human sacrifice⁷¹ and a \$150+ billion a year sex/slave trade⁷² works so hard to keep mankind dependent on the mediocre production of AC current and not to explore telluric, scalar, or plasma currents? They cannot

⁷⁰ [3] Appendix

⁷¹ See SA T. Gunderson Files; vol 1:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/0ByRZ_FN_vit_UUtKV0VqMmlBVE0/view?usp=sharing

⁷² <https://www.humanrightsfirst.org/resource/human-trafficking-numbers>

afford - literally - the end of energy scarcity, because free energy would mean the end of their dark power and grip upon humanity, and in encouraging religious strife, industrialized (for profit) warfare, and culture hatred. They have invested billions, maybe trillions into the formation of “endless” empire which seeks to reduce the majority of mankind into consumer servitude, and have spent as little as possible on electric upgrades such as super-trains, etc... As time has gone on, instead they have reduced access to common chemistry, herbal remedies, and the knowledge of foundational electromagnetism.⁷³

The banishment of Dark Forces is not something that a common person can do, and they will always be overwhelmed the same way a single cell cannot defeat HIV or Hepatitis. It takes a stronger *signal* which could theoretically come from many people working in tandem. But given the System knows how to control the masses through marketing, virality and distraction, this seems very unlikely. Rather, Science and specifically the Technocracy (which has found its own worshipful followers⁷⁴) must provide a strong signal. Will they, though? With their focus on the Internet (digital power and computation), and on self-driving cars, and on spying on people to exploit them (like cattle) for advertiser revenue, creating some type of Minority Report world seems a current priority. It will take a specialized effort to create a juicy signal that is **not militaristic** (though it can and will likely be weaponized) and **not classified or hidden** (like a particle collider facility) which will provide powerful mental and spiritual (ie, psychic) impetus for global human evolution. What the phone did by providing inter-connectivity, and the smart phone did by putting the power of a computer and Internet into the hands of people, even if they were poor and destitute: this technology must do that.

So what will it be? Space travel, as CEO Elon Musk banks upon for his fame and affluence? OR free energy as Tesla tried?

Whatever it is, it will need to use the **full, unleashed power of the force**, and be substantial enough, in this author’s opinion, that it can repel alien and asteroid invasions, solar flare extinction events, and rival the power of hurricanes and volcanoes. It should be something that is spiritually dominant, morally ethical and humanistic, as reachable as a personal phone, as humble as water (figuratively speaking), able to become as necessary as food, and most importantly: *never tarnish in importance*, like a wheel or soap.

Birkeland Polyphase Superweb

Yes that is a made up name. It is merely an *idea*. It does not properly exist. What is it? The idea is merely a reactive super-Internet that utilizes organic AI (rather than programmed by humans and so corruptible), so that it can communicate with pets, people, pet-tree computers, whatever... and pulls energy from an inexhaustible source, like the Solar Wind, via laser-assisted asteroid-charge-nets, into a Birkeland current form, which is transported back to Earth. This is frightening as an idea to globalists until they realize the power it can wield. It is frightening to the commoner or civilian, until they realize the power it can give back to the ordinary person (as guns do in paradoxically stopping more criminals than aiding murderers each year). It is a Mutually Assured Destruction **and Creation** situation which forces people to respect one another. As for the capitalists, they can make money on parts, delivery, service, and insurance credits required to maintain the lives of the astronauts (who will be more than willing to go into space for the adventure of the job). The computational throughput will far exceed fibre, and it should theoretically be quantum computer friendly... even aid us in creating a worldwide quantum ubercomputer, which could then perform calculations (via scaled processing) that would decrypt and encrypt anything, as well as tackle problems we cannot currently even hope to imagine tackling with semiconductor level technology.

⁷³ See E Dollard’s work “True Electromagnetism of Nikola Tesla” but also think of this: when the Weinstein controversy occurred, eventually other movies were put out. Yet as of this writing, “Current Wars,” has not been released.

⁷⁴ Steve Jobs had 2 major movies made about him within a 5 year time period! Not even Jesus can boast of that, lately.

It could power both arm and power the 22nd century and the weapons could ensure no one fights without good cause. It could also increase or decrease weather patterns without dispersants and dangerous chemical aerosols. It could be used to synthesize rare earth metals and transform materials we don't need into ones we do. It could diffuse garbage through atomization and then assist in atomic separation. The energy for the fusion and purification of ores would be easily powered through the Earth core- to-ionospheric coupling. The Earth need not be "mined" but if we chose to do so, wireless battery recharge on-the-fly would be achievable through telluric distribution networks, all powered by BC space-power. Backups such as solar, wind, tide and geothermal or even 5th gen nuclear, would remain in useful stand alone situations. If anything there'd be an energy glut which could enable nano-structure manufacture projects that allows mankind to grow into space.

Most excitingly: it could be used to form atomic syphoning from Venus to Mars, and then terraforming of the two neighbors to create new worlds, with drastically more potential for exploitation and creation of life, even duplicating Earth's menagerie in order to protect it. By repowering Mars and Venus, perhaps one day an anti-Galactic mega-magnetosphere could be created by borrowing or sharing with Jupiter, leading to a greater buffer from cosmic rays which damage DNA.

All of it sounds like science fiction til you realize that this is already what PEMC knows about the Universe. It's just taking this interweb of great possibility and putting it into mankind's hands.

A Cautionary Tale

However, none of this should happen willy nilly. So long as a sizable chunk of the dangerously high-IQ and low-EQ⁷⁵ portion of western society remains at the whim of its violent and hateful tendencies, this is too dangerous an enterprise. So what is the lesson: give up? No, of course not. The cautionary tale is the tale of King Arthur (Arthwys) grandfather.

Long ago, in Wales, King Tewdrig⁷⁶ found himself on the wrong side of the Church. He had killed his brother in battle, and this brother was the favored. Tewdrig was therefore censured and excommunicated. Eventually both made up, and he was pardoned. Now the church had its good reasons (control the king), but what were his motivations? The motivation is clear: kings and heirs don't last. Religions go on *and on* and their influence doesn't wane overnight. They are, as a social control mechanism, ingenious. But they are also, however bad they can be, excellent buffers against despotism which the weak and powerless can never be and heroes can *rarely* be⁷⁷.

Therefore, it is useful, even convenient to take control of the religious power as the wise Constantinople did and apply it in a way that led to mass adoption. As bad as Catholicism was towards some of the people, including the sequestering of wealth and the suppression of science, what existed before was a Dark Age of continuous ignorance, disease, warfare, and tribalism. The Catholic Empire led to a unification of spirit in Europe that eventually led to the Age of Exploration and to both the Renaissance and the Enlightenment. These both led to the end of European colonialism and to industrialization and the modern capitalist movement. Capitalism ended female slavery to the biological limits of menstruation, and it led to material enrichment, if not social and cultural enrichment. It also led to widespread literacy, which has had a lasting effect upon both trees (in saving them) and child. All things hold positive and negative, and the more positive the more negative there must be. However, the greatest good has always come out of unification as a rule (so

⁷⁵ Emotional-quotient: <https://globalleadershipfoundation.com/geit/eitest.html>

⁷⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tewdrig>

⁷⁷ Though many are remembered as despots they may have been heroes before; and though many are remembered as heroes, maybe despots they were. This is the cautionary tale of Genghis the Khan, and of Alexander the Great.

long as it respected diversity of belief and being), whereas the greatest ill and destruction have been borne out of dissolution.⁷⁸

Still, the caution that the State will need to be involved and monitor the situation, and be monitored in return by the *tempered* religious process⁷⁹ to mind for both the end of despotism, and the prevention of tribalism, groupthink, and hive mentalities. Yet, it cannot be avoided for the sake of *going backwards*. Firstly, mankind cannot exist in this current mode forever, or resources will run out. It is a transition ramp-up, or should be, and not a mere Dionysian party for 200 years. Secondly mankind has aspirations, as well as those pesky fears of failure, as set forth by science fiction and fantasy writers. And although not all roads should be explored (such as an AI world war), many should, as they are worthy challenges to the human spirit. Humans will be happy climbing mountains and playing business-sports only so long, and then these billions of souls will desire *more*. The depression of many youths can be tied to their realization that adulthood is less exciting than the video games and fantasies they were brought up to believe (its own form of quasi religion). Many have tried to force-fit the fantasy into reality, but after all Hogwarts is a movie set, or a place at a theme park, and not reality. Reality needs therefore to be reflective of this Jedi-wizard-warrior path, and give a scientific arm to the age-old pursuit of self-reification. What the alchemists of the Age of Pisces did as a counter to the crushing bureaucracy of the Religious Establishment, which then fed a mountain of scientific impetus into a burgeoning exploratory movement, can be replicated in a new age of scientific endeavor. Not one that involves tapping mice brains for dubious gain and obviously unethical technologies which can be used to torture and spy on hostages and suspects (which should be given dignity and presumed innocent until proven guilty), but a scientific endeavor that goes beyond mere cures towards enhancing mankind, and their quality of life as well as reducing suffering where necessary⁸⁰, and augmenting but *safeguarding against death and dismemberment* where desired.⁸¹ It would go a long ways towards utilization of the human spirit of **free will** for the greater good (social contract) as well as personal gain and profit. By protecting the human right of rugged individualism, we can encourage top champion level leaders, such as executives and athletes and piano virtuosos, while also enabling the mediocre to *imagine* they are also a success. We may not be able to fund an 80% guitar hero rate in classrooms, but if students can actively receive the lessons they desire via a holographic projection of a personalized teacher AI that loves them and gives them the individual attention they crave which a human teacher cannot give to 100% of the students... it isn't unreasonable to expect that the non-elite level guitar players will also achieve their aim and then move on to more sophisticated instruments or endeavors. In effect, they will grow up, and by being involved they won't *drop out* or *dope up*. They will not punish themselves for not being the champion American ideal, both macho and the everything-to-everyone which social media currently encourages. Their AI teacher, being organic and comprised of electro-current networking can respond, or at a minimum the child can access the religious teachings that are affirmed to provide succor where needed and discipline where wanted. This will lead to rapid evolution of the children into mysterious people. And while not as ideal as the parents doing all of the education, people are more and more rapidly making their friend, collegial, relationship, and sexual networks via the Internet. There must be a buffer. Connecting the child not to drugs, porn, and sarcastic trolls, but instead to organizational groups of similar interests which will give the advice needed (and prevent bullying when detected or reported), will be key to strengthening the individual and the society **concurrently**.

While all of this does not seem religious, overtly, it is in fact the role previously played by churches. A role which cannot be replaced in a day and a night, and yet is vitally important, according to studies which

⁷⁸ Although given the 20th century histories of China and the USSR, one can easily challenge these assumptions to be in reverse!

⁷⁹ A religion amplified in its understanding of science, but not in its intolerance and forceful conversions!

⁸⁰ Leukemia and other cancers, meningitis etal... , migraines, strokes, Cerebral Palsey, etc...

⁸¹ Athletes and many others must suffer to overcome something in order to compete at a high level and become champions. This is the rule of life. Also children who never suffer are wont to spoil and become depressed and aggressive, narcissistic, and even sociopathic in adulthood.

show the value of churches and spiritual lives to the stability and happiness of couples, marriages, children, and employees.⁸² Again, think of the Blue Zone project, in places such as Sardinia and Okinawa where traditional living yields fantastic longevity and social happiness (overall). No place is perfect, and not everyone will be perfect - many don't want to be, even with abundance around them - but that isn't the point. The point is, with energy all around us, there isn't much reason not to provide opportunity. Unless scarcity creates the condition necessary for growth and maturity, in which case then the vast richness of spiritual energy will need to be provided in ways that respects the path that lead to greatest growth.⁸³

Again all of these types of data can be assessed by a scientific community which accesses the latest data quickly, without having to memorize it, and can compare high and low quality data, evidence, and see studies both as overturned or confirmed, and despite being overturned or confirmed (in case there is missing information that will prove useful to seizing upon an unexplored aspect of the story, or some tangent). By having this data, a cure for common maladies such as melancholy and malaise in youth and young adults can be found as well as for truly potent diseases of the mind, spirit, and body.

Flooding The Body with Light

Returning to the idea of lightening and lighting the Heart, now it can be proposed that a common cure for most maladies which is known in Chinese Medicine as Tong Shen Ming, or as Fa Qi (reiki), is possible without costing the doctor any essence or energy of their own. By learning the secrets of the Charge Distributive Networks, three things can be accomplished:

1. The Birkeland Polyphase Superweb can perform the task of duplication-simulation of the scanned body (electric field, thermo, magnetic, sonic, etc...) to look for diseases, blockages, etc... and compare with known databases and augment those databases if an applied cure works.
2. The current flow from the BPS can serve as a curative function, and "flush" out the body, vaporize parasites, cancer cells, etc... and stimulate the glands, nervous system, etc... on a nano or micro level.
3. The removal of used up "negative" energy, or charge, which will be partially from the unpleasantness of life, and emotional energy, and partially from protons/nuclei, and partially from metabolic waste, can possibly be used for research and learning how nature recycles this energy, to create new renewable (on person) filtration and charge systems.⁸⁴

All of these things made possible by a dual-interaction mechanism between proposed BPS and CDN networking, could lead to truly far out evolutionary benefits. Think of deciphering the language of Gaia via crystals and forests, or of creating massive crystalline storage archives in Yosemite, so that mankind's knowledge remains even in the event of a superflare or nova level radiation event. Upon detecting the event a permanent quantum computer floating in the lattice boots up and clones humanity and provides humanity with nurturance, and re-educates survivors, bringing humanity back quickly for re-learning... rather than it taking thousands of years and a lot of guessing (as it has to get the story mostly in the ballpark). Think of all the eggs currently held in the one basket of Internet (which needs AC power from non-renewables) or paper (which doesn't last): biological study, physics, chemistry, math, psychology, business, strategy, astronomy, law, economics, medicine, religion... all destroyable **today**.

When Gobekli Tepe's citizens buried her, mankind had no agriculture for another 6,000 years. This is how long before Sumer emerged. That is unacceptable given our current abilities, let alone what could be accomplished if we unified under a goal to achieve so much more through mastering our insides (as alchemists

⁸² <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1111/j.1467-9280.2008.02124.x>

⁸³ For example, trees grow tallest when denied light by the canopy above. Living in the shadow is cruel, but necessary. Forest fires help tall trees breed, as well.

⁸⁴ Think of static and motion charged watches or fitbit type devices now in use.

once did) via CDN research, and our space and energy needs via BPS's or other tech that matches the criteria named for creating spirit-worthy, worshipful tech.⁸⁵

Have there ever been technologies worth worshipping? Certainly the wheel was worshiped and the native Americans avoided its use, despite knowing about it in art. Much to their detriment. But what about sails, or guns, or compasses? Compasses make use of the "four winds" (directions), and of magnetism, but they are not as worshiped as they once were. Yet, during the Age of Exploration a compass was as close to a captain as his favorite blade. It seems that the compass is *too humble*, whereas the television is too abusive. Still, mankind has undoubtedly worshiped the sword and the gun. The sword in particular was mystical and wise, and powerful in man's mind - even still (excalibur) - because it was associated with the weapon of the God; with a thunderbolt.

So it must be **visibly powerful**. This is the advantage of utilizing the ionosphere for the BPS. By bringing back the "northern" lights to southern hemispheres, and exchanging massive currents *purposefully* in the sky, mankind will love the night sky again, and not wish to pollute it with purposeless wasted AC. Instead, where people are the street lights being sensitive can light, and where they are not, it can be dark (for the animals). And as light pollution goes, so would lots of other pollutions. What need would there be for the smoke and smog?

The Religion would be fed by a shared mutual appreciation of the sacred spaces, and sacred power, which belongs to the God - now known as the interconnective web of life and energy which pervades the cosmos - and informs people, literally in their life. Their homes each having their own water cycle and filtration system, quantum computing assistant, and power plant... mankind could return to the best loves he will never get over: political banter, sports, and gambling. But also to searching the stars for answers, and questing.

All the comforts of the materialist can be met and the richness will lead to a sort of "old blood" down-regulation of material consumerism. Companies can focus on services and on expansion efforts, instead of on branding battles and package wars which waste chemical and mineral resources and pollute the ground and water, and after all, produce trite, meaningless education for children while providing almost nothing of substance. Think of all the hours wasted in a child's television viewing career **not learning** science or religion, and instead memorizing jingles and associating logos with abstract and baseless ideas on masculinity, femininity, cultural mores, and the side-effects of drugs they hope to never have to use!⁸⁶

Back to Life, Back to Reality

The tale here ends with what could be and demands what *should be done* to achieve it? Well, that depends on the target audience. Most of the audience will likely be people either in science or new age religion, and they may or may not be apt to agree. But it is possible the **power** suggested in the BPS could attract the eyes of the greedy or devilishly devious. In which case I am not going to make the idle threat that misuse will lead to a bad afterlife or some other superstitious claim. I have no idea. But I will remind the reader of the misuse of the atom to create not only the atom bomb but the Hydrogen bomb. The misuse of power there led to a monstrosity that isn't even a fun toy (as automatic firearms are). It's simply a nightmare of cost.

⁸⁵ Television has not proved to be worshipful, though it is worshiped and functions as the modern altar. But it is irresponsibly corporate and gaudy, as well as untrustworthy as a source of information. It has been better to be attached to a computer and the Internet for peer-review of data... but the negatives of brain doping remain a problem.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5362930/>

⁸⁶ The author still personally sings the jingle for a sausage company because it had funny little dancing pigs. Wouldn't this have been better used space if it were a nursery rhyme or gaelic fairy tale, which could be referenced for cultural enjoyment or provide some life lesson (as Aesop's Fables have for the author)? Certainly there isn't much use for all this market-ware except to service corporations, and that is a soulless thing to do to a human child!

waste, threat, and decay. There's almost no benefit to a Hydrogen Bomb. An atomic bomb is sufficient to ward off invasion, and most of the H-bomb's power goes up into the atmosphere.

It isn't even like they can be used against comets right now, as they're all aimed against other humans (to our knowledge). They aren't powering rockets, and they aren't powering cities. Nuclear warheads are a financial deathtrap. They don't even give industrial employment, only governmental.

So could BPS become in the hands of a moron (EQ wise). Psychotic sycophants could easily make a mockery. So it is necessary for us all, with or without a moral religion for agreement, to push for the screening of children and young adults for the tendencies of psychotic and narcissistic behaviors, and remove them from access to the materials needed for all superweapon production and even to access to this paper itself, or others like it. Let psychos be focused upon dominating their neighbors lawn and flower gardens, or upon racing dragsters in shows of domination. But to sit back and act like it is not possible for dangerous minds to misuse these ideas is like imagining that police-work doesn't attract people who enjoy power over others for sadistic reasons. Not screening for psychological markers is as dangerous in the short term as not engineering a religious control mechanism for mankind in this new Information Age and allowing false religions to take over everything and confuse people mentally, spiritually, and bodily. It has, thus far, led to global pollution.⁸⁷

Therefore the author asks the readers to do one thing (other than consider the work and critique it, or present their own ideals, ideas, and test them against the latest research and data): teach others while studying. The ancient formula for peaceful proselytizing has always been study, practice, and teach. It is the formula in the Sermon on the Mount, in Islam, and in the Lotus Sutra. It is the Hero's Journey itself: being disciple and master. This will ensure growth and improvement of mankind, with or without a New Religion.

But if you have time, consider *what would you want in a new religion* if you were to transition from your current one (whatever it is) to a futuristic New Religion, fed not by superstition and misunderstandings of past motifs and myths, as well as mass delusions, but by scientific miracles and the exploration of the cosmos? What if you could feel, see, and live with the Force, daily, without even having to do a pushup or get a tattoo or join a cult or worship an angel? What if it was as real and miraculous as the computer you're reading from (that this was typed upon?) What if the power wasn't confined within wires and transistors, but flowed through you as it once did Tesla, lighting him up for all to see, as he lit a lightbulb with nothing but his bare hand? Tell me that isn't a power that you could get behind, get excited by, and would forsake all the entertainment leprechauns and distraction demons in order to understand more and more. A power coming from the heart of the God *out there*, seen with our telescopes and read about in biology textbooks, full of mystery, law, chaos, and infiniteness? Because the author would - in a heartbeat.

⁸⁷ Pollution of the planet began basically simultaneously to the Industrial era ushered in by the Scientific Period. This is not a coincidence. It is a fact of importance.

Nikola Tesla

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